
Image fusion using a new evolution equation

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Abstract

In this paper, we solve the image fusion problem using a new mathematical model. We reformulate a recent osmosis model using nonlocal differential operators. Experimental results show that the nonlocal model obtained very good qualitative results compared with state-of-the-art models, including modern deep learning techniques.

Keywords: Image restoration, image fusion, Nonlocal differential operators, Energy minimization.

1 Introduction

Our objective is to fuse two grayscale images f (foreground) and b (background), which are real-valued functions defined on the same closed bounded regular domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ (f and b are supposed in $L^\infty(\Omega, (0, +\infty))$). Note that the extension to color images can be easily accomplished by processing each color channel independently. The domain Ω is decomposed into three distinct regions: Ω_f which represents the image region copied from the foreground, Ω_b which represents the image region copied from the background, and Ω_{sb} is a transition region in which f and b are mixed (refer to Figure 1).

Figure 1: Image fusion results. From left to right: background, selected region, foreground, Seamless Poisson Editing [4], our nonlocal osmosis model.

2 Proposed model

We propose a new nonlocal model for image fusion which consists in minimizing the energy:

$$\mathcal{E}(u) := \mathcal{S}(u) + \lambda \mathcal{F}(u), \quad (1)$$

where \mathcal{S} is a fusion term and \mathcal{F} is a fidelity term. These terms are balanced using positive weight λ .

The fusion term: This term is a nonlocal osmosis model:

$$\mathcal{S}(u) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} v(x) \left| \nabla_{NL} \left(\frac{u}{v} \right) \right|^2(x) dx, \quad (2)$$

where

$$v(x) = f^{\alpha(x)}(x) b^{1-\alpha(x)}(x) \quad (3)$$

and α is defined as follows:

$$\alpha(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x \in \Omega_f, \\ G(x), & \text{if } x \in \Omega_{sb}, \\ 0, & \text{if } x \in \Omega_b. \end{cases}$$

where the function G ensures a smooth transition on Ω_{sb} between 0 and 1¹, while $v = f$ on Ω_f and $v = b$ on Ω_b . The function v can be seen as a "rough solution" of the fusion problem.

Fidelity term: To ensure that the solution u should stay close to f in the foreground region, we minimize the following term

$$\mathcal{F}(u) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \frac{\alpha(x)}{v(x)} (f(x) - u(x))^2 dx. \quad (4)$$

In (2), $\nabla_{NL} : \Omega \times \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ stands for a nonlocal gradient which permits to take into account nonlocal interactions between distant pixels. Here, we use the Gilboa operator [3] defined by

$$\nabla_{NL}u(x, y) := (u(y) - u(x)) \sqrt{w(x, y)}, \quad \forall x, y \in \Omega,$$

where $w : \Omega \times \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ is a weight assumed to be symmetric. The inner product of two "vector" functions $v, v_1 : \Omega \times \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined as

$$\langle v, v_1 \rangle := \int_{\Omega \times \Omega} v(x, y) v_1(x, y) dx dy.$$

The magnitude of v is a function $|v| : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by

$$|v|(x) := \sqrt{\int_{\Omega} v(x, y)^2 dy}.$$

The nonlocal divergence $\operatorname{div}_{NL}v : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined as the adjoint of the nonlocal gradient:

$$(\operatorname{div}_{NL}v)(x) = \int_{\Omega} (v(x, y) - v(y, x)) \sqrt{w(x, y)} dy.$$

The nonlocal Laplacian $\Delta_{NL}u$ is a function defined on Ω by

$$\Delta_{NL}u(x) := \frac{1}{2} (\operatorname{div}_{NL} \nabla_{NL}u)(x) = \int_{\Omega} (u(y) - u(x)) w(x, y) dy.$$

where the factor $\frac{1}{2}$ is introduced to be consistent with the graph Laplacian definition.

2.1 Evolution problem

In this section, we derive the evolution equation associated with (1), which can be seen as a "continuous" gradient descent algorithm. We seek a time-dependent solution $u(t, \cdot)$ that evolves over time toward the minimizer of the energy (1).

Proposition 1 For $f, b \in L^\infty(\Omega, \mathbb{R}_+)$, the evolution process associated to 1 is defined as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, x) &= \operatorname{div}_{NL} \left(v(x) \nabla_{NL} \left(\frac{u(t, \cdot)}{v} \right) (x, y) \right) + \lambda \alpha(x) (f(x) - u(t, x)) & \text{in } \Omega_t, \\ u(0, x) &= f(x), & \text{in } \Omega, \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where $\Omega_t = (0, T) \times \Omega$.

Proof 1 Let $\psi \in C_c^\infty(\Omega)$ be a test function and $t > 0$. For convenience, we may drop the the notation of the variable t . We compute the Gâteaux derivative of $\mathcal{E}(u)$ at u in the direction ψ . The Gâteaux variations of \mathcal{F} is straightforward:

$$\mathcal{F}'(u) = \frac{\alpha}{v} (u - f).$$

¹The exact definition of G is given in the Section dedicated to the numerical resolution.

On the other hand, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{S}'(u)(\psi) &= \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{\mathcal{S}(u + t\psi) - \mathcal{S}(u)}{t}, \\
&= \iint_{\Omega \times \Omega} v(x) \left(\frac{u(y)}{v(y)} - \frac{u(x)}{v(x)} \right) \left(\frac{\psi(y)}{v(y)} - \frac{\psi(x)}{v(x)} \right) \omega(x, y) \, dy dx, \\
&= \iint_{\Omega \times \Omega} v(x) \left(\frac{u(y)}{v(y)} - \frac{u(x)}{v(x)} \right) \frac{\psi(y)}{v(y)} \omega(x, y) \, dy dx \\
&\quad - \iint_{\Omega \times \Omega} \left(\frac{u(y)}{v(y)} - \frac{u(x)}{v(x)} \right) \psi(x) \omega(x, y) \, dy dx, \\
&= \iint_{\Omega \times \Omega} v(y) \left(\frac{u(x)}{v(x)} - \frac{u(y)}{v(y)} \right) \frac{\psi(x)}{v(x)} \omega(y, x) \, dx dy \\
&\quad - \iint_{\Omega \times \Omega} \left(\frac{u(y)}{v(y)} - \frac{u(x)}{v(x)} \right) \psi(x) \omega(x, y) \, dy dx, \\
&= \int_{\Omega} \left(-\frac{1}{v(x)} \int_{\Omega} v(x) \left(\frac{u(y)}{v(y)} - \frac{u(x)}{v(x)} \right) w(x, y) \, dy \right) \psi(x) \, dx \\
&\quad + \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{1}{v(x)} \int_{\Omega} \left(v(y) \left(\frac{u(x)}{v(x)} - \frac{u(y)}{v(y)} \right) \right) w(x, y) \, dy \right) \psi(x) \, dx, \\
&= \int_{\Omega} \left(-\frac{1}{v(x)} \operatorname{div}_{NL} \left(v \nabla_{NL} \left(\frac{u}{v} \right) \right) (x) \right) \psi(x) \, dx.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, we obtain:

$$\mathcal{E}'(u) = -\operatorname{div}_{NL} \left(v \nabla_{NL} \left(\frac{u}{v} \right) \right) - \lambda \alpha(f - u).$$

The Euler-Lagrange equation $\mathcal{E}'(u) = 0$ is difficult to solve. Consequently, we use the suboptimal gradient descent procedure

$$\partial_t u(t, x) = -\mathcal{E}'(u).$$

Thus, we obtain the system (5).

3 Numerical resolution

Let Ω_d be a discrete grid associated to the continuous domain Ω :

$$\Omega_d = \{1, \dots, M\} \times \{1, \dots, N\}.$$

We use the following notations:

$$\mathbf{i} = (i_1, i_2) \in \Omega_d, \mathbf{x}_i = (x_{i_1}, y_{i_2}) \in \Omega, u_i \approx u(\mathbf{x}_i), \alpha^i \approx \alpha(\mathbf{x}_i).$$

The image f is approximated by a discrete matrix f_d .

The weight function ω defines a similarity between two pixels \mathbf{x}_i and \mathbf{x}_j by comparing their neighborhoods:

$$\omega_{i,j} = \omega(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j) = \exp \left(-\frac{1}{h^2} \sum_{t_1, t_2 = -r}^r G_{\sigma}(t_1, t_2) (f(\mathbf{x}_{i+t}) - f(\mathbf{x}_{j+t}))^2 \right), \quad (6)$$

where r defines the neighborhood, $\mathbf{t} = (t_1, t_2)$, and $h > 0$ is a scale parameter and G_{σ} is a gaussian function ($G_{\sigma}(t_1, t_2) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma^2} e^{-\frac{t_1^2 + t_2^2}{2\sigma^2}}$, with $\sigma > 0$).

The approximation of the nonlocal Laplacian is given by:

$$\Delta_{NL} u(\mathbf{x}_i) \approx (\Delta_{NL} u)_i = \sum_{j \in \Omega_d} (u_j - u_i) \omega_{i,j}.$$

The nonlocal divergence of $p : \Omega \times \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is approximated by

$$\operatorname{div}_{NL}(p)(\mathbf{x}_i) \approx (\operatorname{div}_{NL}(p))_i = \sum_{j \in \Omega_d} (p_{i,j} - p_{j,i}) \sqrt{\omega_{i,j}}.$$

We approximate space derivative by forward differences and time derivative using explicit Euler method. The discrete iterative scheme of (5) writes:

$$u_i^{n+1} = u_i^n + \frac{dt}{dx} \left((\Delta_{NL} u^n)_i + \sum_{j \in \Omega_d} \frac{v_i}{v_j} u_j^n \omega_{i,j} - \sum_{j \in \Omega_d} \frac{v_j}{v_i} u_i^n \omega_{i,j} \right) + dt \lambda \alpha^i (f_i - u_i^n)$$

where dt , dx are the discretization steps, n is the time index.

Then, the discrete problem can be written as algebraic equations of the form

$$U^{n+1} = \mathbf{A}U^n + \mathbf{P}F,$$

where $U \in \mathbb{R}^m$, $m = M \times N$, is the vector obtained by concatenating the columns of the discrete image u , n is the time index, $F = (f_i)_{1 \leq i \leq m}$ and the initial condition is set to $U^0 = F$.

4 Experimental results

We conducted extensive experiments to evaluate our model and compare it to previous state-of-the-art techniques: Poisson Image Editing [2], Parisotto et al. [4]. We implemented our algorithm using Matlab 2020a, but the weight function had been implemented as a c-mex file (C-program). Simulations have been conducted on a Core i5-4210 (2.60 GHz) processor with 4GO RAM.

Based on an empirical analysis, we determined the values of the parameter λ and found that $\lambda \in [0, 1]$. For the weight function, we choose, in most cases, a patch size of 5×5 , search window of size 7×7 , $\sigma = 0.003$ and the filtering parameter $h = \sigma$.

We used the software and test data provided by the authors^{2, 3, 4}. In some approaches, the authors presented an automatic method for selecting region. However, in this work, we assume that the sub-domain is given to focus on the numerical solution of the nonlocal equation. Let's mention, for the images that have not the same size, we create a new image foreground with the same size of background and with the centroid of selected region in the position with other coordinates.

The function α allows to indicate from which of the two images the structural information comes from. In the case where $\Omega_{sb} = \emptyset$, α is binar, i.e. $\alpha(x) \in \{0, 1\}$, so α vanishes on the pixels of the background image b and is equal to one otherwise. Alternatively, α can be smoothed by means of a Gaussian convolution so as to favour a smooth transition on $\Omega_{sb} \neq \emptyset$.

Experimental results obtained by the nonlocal model are presented on Figure 2 (qualitative evaluation). As demonstrated visually, our method outperforms previous state-of-the-art techniques in most cases. It produces a better skin tone than the seamless Poisson editing model and Parisotto et al. [4] model as showing in Figure 2(a) and Figure 2(b). It is a powerful tool for manipulating colors, two differently colored versions of those images can be mixed seamlessly. For example, in Figure 2(d), our model overcomes the problem of the undesirable visible seam of Parisotto et al. [4] model. An example is shown in Figure 2(e), in which our model can facilitate the transfer of partly transparent objects (the rainbow).

4.1 Comparison with deep learning techniques

We also assess the performance of the proposed image fusion method using the Lytro⁵ dataset. The fusion results of the proposed method are compared with three recently developed fusion algorithms. The first one is GFDF [5]. The second compared algorithm is DCT_EOL [1]. The third method is CNN [6]. All image fusion results⁶ of these algorithms are available online. The results are presented on Figure 3.

³<https://doi.org/10.5201/ipol.2016.163>

⁴<http://cs.brown.edu/courses/cs129/results/proj2/damoreno/>

⁵<https://sandipanweb.wordpress.com/2017/10/03/some-variational-image-processing-possion-image-editing-and-its-applications/>

⁶https://www.researchgate.net/publication/291522937_Lytrio_Multi-focus_Image_Dataset

⁶<https://github.com/xingchenzhang/MFIF>

Figure 2: Image fusion results of different models ((1)-(8)). From left to right: background, selected region, foreground, Seamless Poisson Editing [2], Parisotto et al. [4], nonlocal osmosis model (1).

Figure 3: Qualitative comparison of results of Lytro dataset. (1) and (2) are: Foreground and background. From (3) to (6) are fused images obtained by: GFDF [5], DCT_EOL [1], CNN [6], nonlocal osmosis model (1).

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we presented a novel nonlocal model for image fusion that utilizes nonlocal derivatives in the recently developed osmosis model. Experimental analyses have shown that our proposed model demonstrates its effectiveness and superiority over local image fusion models. Our proposed method provides visually plausible image data fusion that is invariant to multiplicative brightness changes.

References

- [1] M. Amin-Naji and A. Aghagolzadeh. Multi-focus image fusion in dct domain using variance and energy of laplacian and correlation coefficient for visual sensor networks. *Journal of AI and Data Mining*,, pages 33–250, 2018.
- [2] J. Matas Di Martino, Gabriele Facciolo, and Enric Meinhardt-Llopis. Poisson Image Editing. *Image Processing On Line*, pages 300–325, 2016.
- [3] Guy Gilboa and Stanley Osher. Nonlocal operators with applications to image processing. *Multiscale Modeling & Simulation*, 7(3):1005–1028, 2009.
- [4] Simone Parisotto, Luca Calatroni, Aurélie Bugeau, Nicolas Papadakis, and Carola-Bibiane Schönlieb. Variational osmosis for non-linear image fusion. *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, pages 5507–5516, 2020.
- [5] L. Zhang X. Qiu, M. Li and X. Yuan. Guided filter-based multi-focus image fusion through focus region detection. *Signal Processing: Image Communication*, pages 35–46, 2019.
- [6] H. Peng Y. Liu, X. Chen and Z.Wang. Multi-focus image fusion with a deep convolutional neural network. *Information Fusion*,, pages 191–207, 2017.